

ESTIMATION OF NICKEL

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A simple, economic volumetric process for estimating nickel, specially in non-ferrous alloys, is described. It does not require keeping for completion of reaction nor any excess of reagent.

Amongst the methods generally followed for the estimation of nickel, the two more convenient and economical than others are (i) precipitation with dimethylglyoxime and weighing as its nickel salt or NiO; (ii) separation of nickel with the above reagent and titration with NaOH after dissolving the precipitate in excess of H_2SO_4 .

The first method is simple but necessitates addition of excess of the reagent and keeping for 15 minutes to 30 minutes at the boil; for complete precipitation and quick filtration of the Ni salt. standard methods (that of O' Brunck) suggest the use of 7 times, by weight of the reagent, that of the nickel salt theoretically, 1 molecule of Ni combines with two of dimethylglyoxime; therefore 4 times (weight) as much of the reagent as nickel is required.

The second method by Par and Lindgen, however, requires much practice. In case $N/10$ -NaOH is used for back titration, it necessitates the use of $N/10$ - H_2SO_4 for dissolving the nickel precipitate. In that case it requires warming of the solution and sometimes boiling. It has also been observed that sometimes minute specks of precipitate escape dissolution.

Temperature of the Ni solution (in sulphuric acid) is an important factor in final titration. There being no added indicator and the nickel solution itself functioning as one, this raising or lowering of temperature of the solution has much to do with the end-point. The end-point is more sharp above 60° than below it. Further increase in temperature does not show any improvement, on the contrary, too much increase more or less destroys the sharpness of the end-point.

The following is a simplified process for the estimation of nickel, specially in non-ferrous alloys. The process is essentially volumetric and does not require keeping for completion of reaction, nor any excess of reagent.

Procedure

Dissolve 0.2 g. of the sample in 50 c.c. of nitric acid, evaporate nearly to dryness and then take up in 50 c.c. of water. Filter off any precipitate of tin. In the filtrate pass H_2S to separate copper and lead or electrolyse with Pt electrodes. Make up the volume of the filtrate to 200 c.c. (after boiling off H_2S , if any), add 20 c.c. of 25% ammonium chloride solution, 10 c.c. of 20% citric acid solution, and 50 c.c. of ammonia. Warm to $55-60^\circ$ for 5 minutes. Remove from the hot plate, add 5 c.c. of ammonia and titrate with 1% dimethylglyoxime solution. Use a filter paper soaked with dimethylglyoxime solution as an outside indicator. The red colour produced will gradually fade until it will be such as to be visible only in transmitted light. Addition of 3 to 4 drops more will cause disappearance of this colour. This point is taken as the end-point of the titration.

The dimethylglyoxime is similarly standardised against a known nickel or its salt. The following are some results in comparison with the standard precipitation method.

Experiment.	Ni taken.	Nickel found by the			% Error.
		titration.	precipitation.	difference.	
1 Nickel	0'0400 g.	0'03992 g.	0'03997 g.	0'00005	0'12
2 Nickel	0'0300	0'02994	0'02998	0'00004	0'13
3 Cupro-nickel	—	0'05195	0'05220	0'00025	0'50
4 White copper	—	0'02460	0'02449	0'00011	0'06
5 Nickel silver	—	0'02130	0'02120	0'00010	0'05
6 „	—	0'02176	0'02140	0'00036	0'18
7 „	—	0'02082	0'02080	0'00002	0'01
8 „	—	0'02274	0'02260	0'00014	0'07
9 „	—	—	—	—	—
10 „	—	—	—	—	—

Interference

The main element that interferes with this method is copper. Even if the copper is kept in solution as cuprammonium, some dimethylglyoxime is used up in excess of that ordinarily consumed. This is due probably to the formation of a compound of copper with dimethylglyoxime as studied by Kolthoff (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1930, **52**, 2222). This excess can be cut short by slow addition, yet a stage could be reached at which comparison could be made.

Iron in small amounts can be kept suppressed as citrate. The titration can be done in presence of zinc (which up to 40% did not interfere).

The titrations are best done in an automatic filling burette of the baryta type to avoid loss of alcohol due to evaporation.

The method is satisfactory for quick estimations, as well as for economical use of dimethylglyoxime, and can be used with considerable accuracy. A few estimations will enable the operator to detect the end-point correctly.

In presence of appreciable amount of iron, a faint colour is taken as the end-point as it requires 0'1 to 0'2 c.c. before it is completely decolourised, while in the absence of iron only 0'025 to 0'05 c.c. will give the end-point.

Recovery of Dimethylglyoxime from Nickel Precipitate

The method is economic and simple and saves the trouble of carrying out the complicated process of *breaking* with acid and regenerating dimethylglyoxime. The only reagent employed is a sulphureted hydrogen Kipp and a concentration or distillation arrangement.

Procedure.—The Ni precipitate is suspended in water and warmed. A rapid stream of H₂S is passed through it until cold. If the gas bubbles are not sufficient to effectively stir the suspended matter, a mechanical arrangement may be employed. The whole mass is then digested under pressure for nearly an hour. The filtrate is concentrated to get the dimethylglyoxime. It can further be purified by recrystallisation from alcohol.

The yield is satisfactory. A better yield is obtained if the whole operation is carried out in alcohol medium rather than water, with special arrangements to avoid too much loss of the suspending liquid.

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